

Towards Efficient Keyframe Selection for News Video Captioning

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Abstract—Vision-language models are increasingly used for video captioning, but their reliance on uniform frame sampling introduces inefficiencies. Uniform sampling risks overlooking informative frames rich in textual or structural cues while redundantly processing visually similar frames, leading to inflated computational costs and degraded caption quality. To address this, we propose a layout-aware keyframe selection method that integrates shot segmentation with layout detection to identify frames containing the most semantically informative visual and textual elements. By prioritizing event-rich frames, our approach reduces redundancy while preserving critical contextual information for downstream captioning. On a benchmark of English-language news videos, our method achieved an event matching F1 score of 0.961, a 14% improvement over uniform sampling, while reducing the number of selected frames by 12.78% compared to state-of-the-art methods. These findings underscore the importance of task-specific frame selection in optimizing VLM-based video captioning, particularly for domains rich in on-screen text such as news broadcasts.

Index Terms—Video summarization, video captioning, vision-language models, keyframe selection

I. INTRODUCTION

Vision-language models (VLMs) [2, 7, 9, 10, 18] are increasingly used to generate captions for videos, but the common practice of uniform frame sampling is inefficient, presenting two key issues: it may miss more informative frames that were not sampled and may result in redundancy by selecting frames that are similar to those already chosen. Processing repetitive or low-information frames inflates computational cost and token usage without improving caption quality. This is critical as the self-attention mechanism in many VLMs scales quadratically with the number of input tokens, making frame reduction a necessity for efficiency.

This issue is particularly relevant for videos rich in on-screen text or structured visuals, such as news broadcasts. A closely related area of research is keyframe selection for video summarization, which focuses on extracting a representative subset of frames that encapsulate the essential content of a video. However, existing keyframe selection methods [1, 5, 13, 14] are mainly designed for frame sampling rather than to generate accurate textual descriptions. As a result, their effectiveness for this specific task has not been thoroughly explored.

In this work, we introduce a benchmark and evaluation metric designed to assess how effectively selected frames support event-level captioning. We also evaluate existing

keyframe selection methods (including LMSKE, INCEPTION, and uniform sampling) as baselines and propose a two-step method that combines shot segmentation with layout detection (LD) to select the most informative frames.

There are two main contributions of this work: (1) it introduces a benchmark and metric for evaluating frame selection in event-level captioning, (2) it proposes a layout-aware approach that selects informative frames via shot segmentation and visual structure analysis.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews prior research on video summarization, captioning, and VLMs. In Section III, we describe our proposed two-step keyframe selection method, which combines shot segmentation and LD, along with a novel evaluation approach based on semantic alignment. Section IV presents our experimental setup and results, demonstrating that our method achieves competitive caption quality with fewer frames. Finally, we conclude in Section V with a discussion of our findings and suggestions for future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

Efficient video captioning is a complex task that involves interpreting both visual content and temporal structure to generate coherent textual descriptions while using as few frames as possible. Three fundamental components of this pipeline are shot boundary detection, keyframe selection, and evaluation.

Shot boundary detection refers to the process of segmenting a video into discrete shot sequences of uninterrupted captured frames. This step is crucial for identifying scene changes and organizing a video into semantically meaningful units. Models like TransNetV2 [12] provide deep learning-based methods to detect these boundaries accurately and efficiently. In our work, shot segmentation serves as the foundation for isolating visually coherent segments, each of which is then analyzed for keyframe selection.

Keyframe selection, often studied under the umbrella of video summarization, involves identifying a minimal set of frames that effectively represent the entire video. Traditional summarization methods [1, 5, 13] aim to capture visual diversity or importance based on appearance or motion, without necessarily accounting for downstream tasks such as captioning. Although these approaches reduce redundancy and computational load, they do not explicitly optimize for selecting frames that improve textual descriptions, which is the goal of this work.

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Evaluation techniques for video captioning often rely on metrics such as BLEU and METEOR [8, 15], which measure n-gram overlap between generated and reference captions. However, these metrics are limited in capturing semantic similarity and are sensitive to paraphrasing. In contrast, video summarization benchmarks such as SumMe [6] and TVSum [11] evaluate the quality of frame selection based on visual similarity to human-selected summaries. Neither of these benchmarks are suitable for captioning tasks due to their lack of visual and semantic alignment. To address this gap, our work introduces a semantic evaluation approach based on event alignment using embedding similarity and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW), enabling a more meaningful assessment of caption quality derived from selected frames.

In addition, recent advances in VLMs [9, 16, 17] has made it possible to generate coherent captions from a set of input frames. These models often support multi-image input, enabling a deeper understanding of video content. Although VLMs provide strong language modeling capabilities, the quality of their output is highly dependent on the informativeness of the input frames. This affirms the importance of selecting frames that preserve critical visual and textual cues.

In general, our work sits at the intersection of these areas. We leverage shot boundary detection to structure the video, introduce a layout-aware frame selection strategy tailored for VLM input, and propose an evaluation method that more accurately reflects the quality of the generated textual descriptions.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Frame Sampling Pipeline

To efficiently identify the most informative visual content for captioning, we employ a two-stage keyframe selection pipeline designed to extract the most informative frames while minimizing redundancy (outlined in Algorithm 1). By prioritizing frames containing the greatest diversity of unique object classes, our method maximizes the information richness of each keyframe while minimizing redundancy and computational load.

The process begins by *Extracting Frames and Detecting Shot Boundaries*, where a deep learning model partitions the video into coherent temporal segments, each corresponding to a distinct shot or scene transition. Partitioning the video into these segments is a critical indicator of scene boundaries, often indicating changes in topic, location, or host. This step of Algorithm 1 allows the portrayal of a consistent visual narrative for VLMs. Once segmented, frames within each shot are uniformly sampled to 2 frames per second (FPS) as a pre-processing step to reduce computational overhead while maintaining sufficient temporal granularity. Sampling at 2 FPS also minimizes the load on the LD model in the next step. We did not conduct in-depth experiments on varying the FPS per shot, leaving this for potential future work.

The next step is to *Select Representative Frame for Each Segment*. For each downsampled frame, we apply a DETR-based [3] LD model [4] to identify key visual and textual elements, such as objects, text regions, and graphical structures.

Fig. 1. Result from a LD model used on a frame from a news video.

Algorithm 1 Segment Video and Select Key Frames Based on Layout Objects

Require: *video_file*

Ensure: *selected_frames*

```

1: Step 1: Extracting Frames and Detecting Shot Boundaries
2: frames  $\leftarrow$  ExtractFrames(video_file)
3: segments  $\leftarrow$  TransNet(frames)
4:
5: Step 2: Select Representative Frame for Each Segment
6: for each segment  $\in$  segments do
7:   max_classes  $\leftarrow$  0
8:   best_frame  $\leftarrow$  FirstFrame(segment)
9:   for each frame  $\in$  segment do
10:    processed_frame  $\leftarrow$  PreprocessFrame(frame)
11:    detections  $\leftarrow$  LayoutDetection(processed_frame)
12:    unique_classes  $\leftarrow$  CountClasses(detections)
13:    if unique_classes > max_classes then
14:      max_classes  $\leftarrow$  unique_classes
15:      best_frame  $\leftarrow$  frame
16:    end if
17:  end for
18:  Append(selected_frames, best_frame)
19: end for
20:
21: return selected_frames

```

Frames with more detected layout classes, such as captions, footnotes, and titles, are considered more informative. An example of LD output is shown in figure 1. Finally, during **frame selection**, we choose the frame within each shot that contains the highest number of layout classes, ensuring that the selected frames capture the most relevant visual and textual information.

B. Evaluation Methodology

We propose a novel evaluation methodology for assessing the quality of keyframe selection in video descriptions. Our evaluation is based on a dataset of 11 English-language news

videos from YouTube (e.g., 9News, NBC), each approximately 65 seconds in duration. The descriptions of each video were generated using the MiniCPM VLM [17] and verified by human annotators. These ground-truth descriptions are structured as ordered lists of key events.

Each video is segmented into shots, which we treat as discrete events. To ensure comparability with methods lacking explicit shot segmentation, we apply a consistent shot-detection process and aggregate frames accordingly.

1) *Event Matching Score*: We measured the similarity between generated and ground truth event descriptions using an event-matching score, computed via cosine similarity and DTW, as detailed in Algorithm 2.

The evaluation proceeds as follows:

- **Embedding Normalization (Lines 1–6)**: Both ground truth and generated descriptions are converted into embeddings using OpenAI’s text embedding model (text-embedding-3-large). These embeddings are then L2-normalized to ensure consistent similarity calculations (see `Normalize()` function, Line 4).
- **Distance Metric (Lines 7–9)**: Cosine distance is used to compare embeddings.
- **Temporal Alignment (Line 10)**: DTW is applied to the full temporal sequence of normalized event embeddings for the ground truth and the generated description.
- **Match Extraction (Lines 11–15)**: For each aligned pair, we compute the cosine similarity (line 13) and keep matches exceeding a similarity threshold θ (Line 14). Each event description is matched at most once.
- **F1 Score Computation (Lines 26–31)**: Precision and recall are calculated from the number of matches and combined into an F1 score (line 22).

This process ensures fair and flexible comparison by accommodating variations in the number of generated versus ground truth events. See Figure 2 for a high-level overview.

2) *Rationale for Evaluation Approach*: Traditional evaluation techniques for video summarization typically involve comparing selected frames to human-chosen keyframes based on visual features, such as color distribution. In contrast, our focus is on using these frames to generate accurate, descriptive captions, necessitating a more semantic evaluation method. Our approach ensures that the selected frames are both visually representative and semantically aligned with the ground-truth event descriptions.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experimental Setup

To evaluate the performance of our proposed method, we compared it with state-of-the-art keyframe selection algorithms, including LMSKE [13] and INCEPTION [5], as well as a uniform sampling baseline. LMSKE selects frame based on motion saliency (how much as frame stands out comparative to adjacent frames), whereas INCEPTION focuses on semantic/visual diversity by ensuring different objects/scenes are covered, regardless of adjacent frames. The evaluation was

Algorithm 2 Evaluate Event Matching via Cosine Similarity and DTW

Require: $gt_embeddings, gen_embeddings, threshold$

Ensure: $f1_score$

```

1:  $gt \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(gt\_embeddings)$ 
2:  $gen \leftarrow \text{Normalize}(gen\_embeddings)$ 
3: function NORMALIZE( $embeddings$ )
4:    $norms \leftarrow \text{L2Norm}(embeddings) + 1e-8$ 
5:   return  $embeddings/norms$ 
6: end function
7: function COSINEDISTANCE( $x, y$ )
8:   return  $1 - \text{DotProduct}(x, y)$ 
9: end function
10:  $distance, cost, acc\_cost, path \leftarrow \text{DTW}(gt, gen, \text{COSINEDISTANCE})$ 
11:  $gt\_indices, gen\_indices \leftarrow path$ 
12:  $matches \leftarrow []$ 
13:  $matched\_gt \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
14:  $matched\_gen \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
15: for each  $(i, j) \in (gt\_indices, gen\_indices)$  do
16:   if  $i \in matched\_gt$  or  $j \in matched\_gen$  then
17:     continue
18:   end if
19:    $sim \leftarrow \text{DotProduct}(gt[i], gen[j])$ 
20:   if  $sim \geq threshold$  then
21:     Append( $matches, (i, j)$ )
22:     Add  $i$  to  $matched\_gt$ 
23:     Add  $j$  to  $matched\_gen$ 
24:   end if
25: end for
26:  $tp \leftarrow \text{Length}(matches)$ 
27:  $total\_gt \leftarrow \text{Length}(gt)$ 
28:  $total\_gen \leftarrow \text{Length}(gen)$ 
29:  $precision \leftarrow tp/total\_gen$  if  $total\_gen > 0$  else 0.0
30:  $recall \leftarrow tp/total\_gt$  if  $total\_gt > 0$  else 0.0
31:  $f1\_score \leftarrow$  if  $precision + recall > 0$  then  $2 \cdot (precision \cdot recall)/(precision + recall)$  else 0.0
32: return  $f1\_score$ 

```

conducted using the event-matching score detailed in Section III-B. We measured two key metrics: the event-matching F1 score and the average number of frames sampled per video.

In our experiments, we used different cosine similarity thresholds of $\theta = 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9$ for matching pairs, as defined in Section III-B. These values were chosen to represent a high range of similarity within the overall range of 0 to 1. We also used the TransNetV2 [12] model for shot segmentation and detr-layout-detection [4] for LD.

The experiments were conducted on a system with an Intel Core i5-13400F processor, 128 GB DDR4 RAM, and two NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPUs. The VLM used in our study was a 4-bit quantized MiniCPM-V-2.6 [17], loaded via the Transformers library (version 4.47).

Fig. 2. Overview of our evaluation methodology. Instead of comparing keyframes directly, we assess the alignment of generated and ground truth event descriptions.

B. Results

Tables I-V present the evaluation results. Our method, which combines TransNetV2 for shot segmentation and LD for frame selection, achieved comparable scores while using the fewest number of frames per video on $\theta = 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8$. At the extremely high threshold $\theta = 0.9$ in Table V, we observed a larger decrease in the F1 score, but still sampled fewer frames overall. We provide a case study shown in Fig. 3 and 4.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF F1 SCORES AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF FRAMES
SAMPLED PER VIDEO USING $\theta = 0.5$.

Algorithm	F1	Avg. Sampled
Ours (TransNet + LD)	0.961	13.27
LMSKE	0.957	15.73
INCEPTION	0.930	13.27
Uniform Sampling	0.843	13.27

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF F1 SCORES AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF FRAMES
SAMPLED PER VIDEO USING $\theta = 0.6$.

Algorithm	F1	Avg. Sampled
Ours (TransNet + LD)	0.942	13.27
LMSKE	0.938	15.73
INCEPTION	0.916	13.27
Uniform Sampling	0.826	13.27

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF F1 SCORES AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF FRAMES
SAMPLED PER VIDEO USING $\theta = 0.7$.

Algorithm	F1	Avg. Sampled
Ours (TransNet + LD)	0.898	13.27
LMSKE	0.883	15.73
INCEPTION	0.839	13.27
Uniform Sampling	0.784	13.27

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF F1 SCORES AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF FRAMES
SAMPLED PER VIDEO USING $\theta = 0.8$.

Algorithm	F1	Avg. Sampled
Ours (TransNet + LD)	0.664	13.27
LMSKE	0.664	15.73
INCEPTION	0.633	13.27
Uniform Sampling	0.580	13.27

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF F1 SCORES AND AVERAGE NUMBER OF FRAMES
SAMPLED PER VIDEO USING $\theta = 0.9$.

Algorithm	F1	Avg. Sampled
Ours (TransNet + LD)	0.107	13.27
LMSKE	0.176	15.73
INCEPTION	0.098	13.27
Uniform Sampling	0.133	13.27

TABLE VI
TOTAL TIME TAKEN IN SECONDS FOR EACH METHOD DURING
EVALUATION.

Algorithm	Time Taken (seconds)
Ours (TransNet + LD)	160.42s
LMSKE	6771.44s
INCEPTION	154.24s
Uniform Sampling	1.88s

C. Observations

We observe that our method yields greater performance gains when $\theta \leq 0.7$, while sampling equal or fewer frames. We attribute this advantage to the nature of news videos, which are rich in textual content, such as headlines and infographics. However, our method may be less effective for other video types, such as one-shot movie clips, where textual elements are scarcer.

In the context of news videos, where clip transitions tend to follow a more consistent structure, our approach generates significantly more informative captions than LMSKE (indicated in Fig. 3 and 4). Although LMSKE is capable of producing general descriptions, it is unable to sample frames that provide maximum context. For example, in Fig. 3, it omits key details such as the exact cause of the flood, the volume of rainfall, and its duration, instead focusing on irrelevant elements such as the kayak brand, therefore distracting from the narrative of the overall news video. In contrast, our method successfully incorporates these critical contextual features while also including the relevant information captured by LMSKE. This highlights the advantage of our method and demonstrates how drastically a news video's contents can be presented inaccurately or incorrectly when methods that use low-information frame sampling are utilized.

Our evaluation methodology focuses on assessing the text descriptions generated from the sampled frames. In contrast, traditional video summarization evaluations primarily compare visual frames. Although our approach ensures informative textual descriptions, traditional evaluation methods may be more

appropriate, particularly when the objective is not to convert sampled frames into textual summaries. This is highlighted in Table VI, where the fastest algorithm was uniform sampling (which selects frames at fixed intervals without considering scene changes, making it extremely fast but with lower semantic coverage) and the slowest algorithm was LMSKE (which utilizes a more descriptive, adaptive process that yields keyframes with better semantic coverage and minimal redundancy, at the cost of high processing time). Our method aims to balance speed and accuracy for an effective holistic model.

A limitation of our method is its dependence on the performance of VLMs used for text generation. The evaluation process is also computationally expensive and time-intensive and requires inference with large VLMs. Our method also assumes that the number of layout classes is perfectly correlated to informational value. This may not hold for all scenarios, such as in cases where a frame with one critical piece of text (e.g. "ALERT") may be more important than a frame with several common objects.

Future work could focus on expanding the test set by incorporating more video description pairs and utilizing audio energy change detection to refine shot segmentation boundaries. Further experimentation testing if larger VLMs are more robust to noisy frame selection, therefore potentially reducing the need for aggressive pruning.

Sampled Frame From Baseline (LMSKE):

VLM Frame Description: "The video captures a scene from Carolina Beach, North Carolina, where a person is navigating through floodwaters using a kayak. The kayak is prominently colored in shades of orange and pink, with the words "OCEAN KAYAK" visible on its side, indicating the brand of the vessel. The individual in the kayak is wearing a life jacket and appears to be using a double-bladed paddle to propel themselves through the water. In the background, there is a dark-colored SUV partially submerged, suggesting the extent of the flooding. The water's surface is rippled, likely due to the movement of the kayak. The overcast sky implies that the weather conditions may have contributed to the flooding. There is no visible text providing additional context or information about the situation."

Fig. 3. Case study of a frame selected using LMSKE as the baseline. The VLM frame description lacks additional context that was present in the news video—as shown in Fig. 4, by selecting a more descriptive frame, a more accurate frame description was produced.

Sampled Frame From Our Method:

VLM Frame Description: "The video depicts a scene of severe flooding in Carolina Beach, North Carolina, following a storm that brought heavy rainfall to the area. A person is seen kayaking through the flooded streets, using a double-bladed paddle to navigate through the water. The kayak is colored in shades of pink and orange, and the individual is wearing a life jacket for safety. In the background, there are parked cars partially submerged, indicating the depth of the floodwaters. The weather appears overcast, suggesting ongoing or recent rainfall. A news ticker at the bottom of the screen provides additional context, stating that severe storms moved through central North Carolina on Monday, causing widespread flooding in some areas. It mentions that in parts of Carolina Beach, 18 inches of rain fell in just 12 hours. The footage is part of a news broadcast, as indicated by the "NBC NOW" logo in the corner."

Fig. 4. In this case study, a frame sampled using our method, unlike the baseline in Fig. 3, includes a critical textual cue, allowing the VLM to produce a more accurate interpretation of the frame and the entire video. The text in green is the additional information our method produced for the description, as a result of choosing a richer frame for selection.

V. CONCLUSION

This work addresses the challenge of efficient keyframe selection for video captioning, particularly in news broadcasts rich in textual and visual information. We propose a two-step method that combines shot segmentation and LD to select the most informative frames while minimizing redundancy. To evaluate the effectiveness of this approach, we introduce a textual-semantic evaluation methodology based on embedding similarity and DTW, aligning more closely with the objective of producing high-quality textual descriptions.

Experiments show that the proposed method achieves competitive or superior performance in event-matching F1 scores while sampling fewer frames than existing baselines. This efficiency highlights the importance of selecting semantically rich frames rather than relying on uniform or appearance-based sampling alone.

Despite its strengths, the approach depends on the accuracy of LD and the quality of VLMs, which may limit its effectiveness in non-news domains. Future work may extend this methodology to other video genres and incorporate adaptive sampling strategies that dynamically account for content diversity. We also plan to expand the benchmark with a broader set of annotated videos and experiment with emerging multimodal models to further enhance captioning performance.

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